

Beauty of Magic Squares: 3888-Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Order 132 - Part 1

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The work is also available at author's site:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=18372>

Abstract

*This paper presents a systematic construction of **multiple order bordered magic squares** at orders 20, 30, 42, 56, 72, 90, 110 and 132. for a full structural summary). Unlike classical block-wise bordered magic squares, which are built as multiples of a single block size, the structures explored here incorporate successive borders drawn from magic squares of **different** orders — specifically orders 3 through 11 — each contributing a distinct structural layer.*

*The innermost core is a magic square of order 12 formed by different-sum magic squares of order 3. Successive borders of orders 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10 and 11 are then applied; **even-order borders** consist of **equal-sum**, while **odd-order borders** consist of **different-sum** magic squares. In case of order 8 and 10, some of the magic squares are with different sums. The combinatorial multiplicity of border types at each level yields a hierarchy of distinct configurations:*

The further study of multiple order bordered magic squares of orders 144 are given in details in the reference list.

Keywords: magic squares, bordered magic squares, pandiagonal magic squares, block-wise construction, multiple order borders, combinatorial enumeration, recreational mathematics.

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1 Introduction

A **magic square** of order n is an arrangement of n^2 distinct integers in an $n \times n$ grid such that the sums of each row, each column, and both main diagonals are equal. This common value is called the **magic constant** (or magic sum), usually denoted S . For a magic square containing the consecutive integers $1, 2, \dots, n^2$, the magic constant is

$$S = \frac{n(n^2 + 1)}{2}. \tag{1}$$

Magic squares have fascinated mathematicians, artists, and philosophers for millennia, appearing in ancient texts. Two constructions are central to the present work.

Definition 1.1 (Bordered magic square). *A magic square is said to be **bordered** if the removal of any outermost border of cells leaves a smaller magic square. All entries are consecutive integers.*

Definition 1.2 (Block-wise bordered magic square). *A magic square is **block-wise bordered** if each border layer is not a single cell wide but is composed of smaller magic squares used as building blocks.*

During past years author [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10] worked with **block-wise** magic squares from orders 12 to 47. Author [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16] also worked with **bordered** magic squares. The study on **bordered** magic squares is extended to **block-bordered** magic squares [17, 18, 19]. This is specially done for the magic squares of orders p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. This study is still extended to **block-wise bordered** magic squares [20, 21, 22, 23]. Some connection with Pythagorean triples and area-representations are also made [25, 26, 27, 28, 29]. The main property of **bordered** magic squares is that if we remove external borders, still we get **sub-bordered** magic squares, i.e., each layer in itself lead us to magic squares. In many cases, the properties of **bordered** magic square are separated by **even** and **odd** orders magic squares. In many cases, we get good properties for the **even** order **bordered** magic squares. In some cases, we have to use fractional numbers to reach minimum perfect square sum of entries. For more study on **bordered** magic squares refer H. White's web-site [3].

The idea of bordered magic squares is already discussed by H. White's web-site [3] where the borders are of **single digits**. Borders multiples of even numbers starting from order 4 are done extensively by author [25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30].

1.1 Summary of Bordered Magic Squares

1.1.1 Odd Numbers Multiples

- **Single Digit:** Bordered magic squares based on single digit [11, 12, 3].
- **Three Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 3 [30].
- **Five Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 5 [32].
- **Seven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 7 [34].
- **Nine Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 9 [36].
- **Eleven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 11 [38].
- **Thirteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 13 [40].
- **Fifteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 15 [42].
- **Seventeen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 17 [44].
- **Nineteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 19 [46].

1.1.2 Even Numbers Multiples

- **Two Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic rectangles multiples of 2 [115, 116, 117, 118, 118, 119, 120].
- **Four Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 4 [25, 31].
- **Six Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 6 [26, 33].
- **Eight Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 8 [27, 35].
- **Ten Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 10 [28, 37].
- **Twelve Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 12 [29, 39].
- **Fourteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 14 [41].
- **Sixteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 16 [43].
- **Eighteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 18 [45].
- **Twenty Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 20 [47].

The advantage in working with even number multiples is that we can work with equal sums blocks of magic squares.

The aim of this work is to bring multiple order **bordered** magic squares of orders 20, 30, 42, 56, 72, 90, 110 and 132. Let see below how it is done.

See below the details of above multiple order bordered magic square.

• **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**

1. Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.

• **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**

1. In this case, we have considered two types of magic squares of order 4.

(a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4.

(b) The second is formed by two equal sums magic sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 resulting in a magic square of order 4. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 20

• **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**

1. In this case, we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 5.

(a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5.

(b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 5, where there are two **equal sums magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner.

(c) The third is **single-layer bordered** magic square with magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 30

• **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**

1. In this case also we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 6.

(a) The first is normal magic square of order 6.

(b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 6, where there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner with two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .

(c) The third one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 42

• **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**

1. In this case, we have considered 5 different types of magic squares of order 7.

(a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7.

(b) The second is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle and 4 equal sums **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 .

(c) The third is a **cornered** magic square of order 7 composed of another **cornered** magic square of order 5 with magic squares of order 3 at the upper-left corner. Two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 .

(d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7 with magic square of order 3 in the middle. Also there are four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 . This type of magic squares we call as **cyclic-double-layer** magic square of order 7.

(e) The fifth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 56.

• **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 8.

- (a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 formed by four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.
- (b) The second is a **cornered** magic square of order 8, where there is again a **cornered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×6 are of equal sums in each case.
- (c) The third is a **double-layer bordered** magic square with **pandiagonal** with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. It has 2 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×8 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .
- (d) The fourth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 with a magic square of order 4 in the middle. This magic square of order 4 is again composed two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . The magic square of order 4 also have four equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×6 . Since it is formed by only **strips** of equal width, we call it a **striped** magic square of order 8.
- (e) The fifth one is four equal sums magic squares of order 4, where each magic square of order 4 is formed by two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . Since it is formed by only magic rectangles of equal width it is known as **striped** magic square.
- (f) The sixth one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic square of order 72.

• **6th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 9**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9.

- (a) The first is composed of 9 **semi-magic** squares of order 3 resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9.
- (b) The second is a cornered magic square, where magic squares of orders 7 and 5 are also **cornered** magic squares at the upper-left corner having magic square of order 3.
- (c) The third is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 having **cornered** magic square of order 5 in the middle. Two **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 and two **magic rectangles** of orders 2×5 are of equal sums in each case.
- (d) The fourth is again a **double-layer bordered** with **single-layer** bordered magic square of order 5 at the middle. The external border is composed of 2 **magic rectangles** of order 2×9 and two **magic rectangles** of order 2×5 . Both are of equal sums in each case. In the middle there is a magic square of order 3.
- (e) The fifth is again a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 with external bordered as 4 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×7 . In the middle there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. This kind of magic square we call as **cyclic-type double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9
- (f) The sixth is a normal **single-layer** bordered magic square of order 9 having magic square of order 3 in the middle.

• **7th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 10**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 10.

- (a) First one is a **traditional** magic square of order 10.
- (b) The second one is a **cornered** magic square of order 10, where magic squares of orders 8 and 6 are also **cornered** magic squares at the upper-left corner having magic square of order 4.
- (c) The third is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 10 having **single-layer** magic square of order 6 in the middle. Four magic rectangles of order 2×8 are of equal sums magic sums. This kind of magic square we call as **cyclic-double-layer bordered** magic square of order 10.
- (d) The fourth one is again a **double-layer bordered** with **cornered** magic squares of order 6 in the middle. It contains magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner. The external border is composed of 2 **magic rectangles** of order 2×10 and two **magic rectangles** of order 2×6 . Both are of equal sums in each case.
- (e) The fifth one is again a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 10 embedded with a **striped** magic square of order 8 composed 4 equal sums magic squares of order 4 or 8 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 .
- (f) The sixth is a normal **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 10 having magic square of order 4 in the middle.

• **8th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 11**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 11.

- (a) First one is a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 11 with magic square of order 3 is in the middle. The 4 magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 4 magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal magic sums in each case.
- (b) The second one is a **cornered** magic square of order 11, where magic squares of orders 9, 7 and 5 are also **cornered** at the upper-left corner with magic square of order 3. The 2 magic rectangles of orders 2×3 , 2 of order 2×5 , 2 of order 2×7 and 2 of order 2×9 are of equal sums in each case.
- (c) The third one is again a **double-layer bordered** magic squares of orders 11 and 7 having magic square of order 3 in the middle. In this case the 2 magic rectangles of orders 2×11 , 4 of order 2×7 and 2 of order 2×3 are of equal magic sums in each case. These types of magic squares sometimes we call as **flat-double-layer bordered** magic squares.
- (d) The fourth is a **cyclic-double-layer bordered** with magic square of order 3 in the middle. The 4 magic rectangles of order 2×9 and 4 of order 2×5 are of equal sums in each case.
- (e) The fifth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a magic square of order 9 composed of 9 equal sums magic squares of order 3.
- (f) The sixth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 11 having magic square of order 3 in the middle.

Below summarises the construction levels.

- **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**

- Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.

- **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**

- In this case we have considered two different types of magic squares of order 4. Combining with magic square of order 12 we have **2-different types** of magic squares of order 20.

- **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**

- In this case, we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 5. Combining with 3 magic squares of order 20 we have **6-different types** of magic squares of order 20.

- **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**

- In this case also we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 6. Combining with 6 magic squares of order 30 we have **18-different types** of magic squares of order 42.

- **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**

- In this case, we have considered 5-different ways of magic squares of order 7. Combining with 18 magic squares of order 42 we have **90-different types** of magic squares of order 56.

- **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**

- In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares. Combining with 90 magic squares of order 56 we have **540-different types** of magic squares of order 72.

- **6th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 9**

- In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9. Combining with 540 magic squares of order 90 we have $6 \times 540 = 3240$, i.e., **3240-different types** of magic squares of order 90.

- **7th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 10**

- In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 10. Combining with 3240 magic squares of order 90 we have $6 \times 3240 = 19440$, i.e., **19440-different types** of magic squares of order 110.

- **8th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 11**

- In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 11. Combining with 19440 magic squares of order 90 we have $6 \times 19440 = 116640$, i.e., **116640-different types** of magic squares of order 132.

The total count at each level equals the product of all variant counts up to that level:

$$N_{\text{ord. 110}} = 1 \times 2(4) \times 3(5) \times 3(6) \times 5(7) \times 6(8) \times 6(9) \times 6(10) \times 6(11) = 116640. \quad (2)$$

More details of last border i.e., 8th border of magic squares of order 11 are given in the following section. Here we observe that instead of 19440 we calculated only 3888 magic squares of order 110. Same here, instead of 116640 magic square of order 132, we shall again construct only 3888, i.e., $6 \times 648 = 3888$ magic squares of order 132. See below the details.

2 Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Order 132

In order to get **bordered magic squares** of order 132, we used following six different types of magic squares of order 11:

11	mgc											671	11	mgc											671
	112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	105	17	671		58	63	62	54	68	43	79	87	35	13	109	671
	10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	20	102	671		65	61	57	55	67	78	44	25	97	104	18	671
	100	22	85	79	42	55	44	50	72	94	28	671		60	59	64	72	50	75	47	24	98	8	114	671
	8	114	37	43	80	67	78	40	82	31	91	671		56	52	53	73	71	38	84	89	33	3	119	671
	107	15	49	73	62	63	58	76	46	24	98	671		66	70	69	51	49	39	83	92	30	106	16	671
	96	26	38	84	57	61	65	70	52	111	11	671		81	37	40	76	77	74	42	29	93	5	117	671
	35	87	66	56	64	59	60	69	53	25	97	671		41	85	82	46	45	80	48	23	99	105	17	671
	104	18	71	51	83	75	45	48	54	19	103	671		21	96	91	27	88	90	22	86	28	108	14	671
	6	116	81	41	39	47	77	74	68	120	2	671		101	26	31	95	34	32	100	94	36	107	15	671
	4	118	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671		120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671
	89	33	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671		2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

11	mgc											671
21	23	113	106	5	115	1	102	2	94	89	671	
101	99	9	16	117	7	121	20	120	28	33	671	
87	35	37	56	83	77	44	79	51	14	108	671	
4	118	85	66	39	45	78	43	71	112	10	671	
86	36	50	72	60	59	64	46	76	110	12	671	
11	111	81	41	65	61	57	84	38	27	95	671	
105	17	52	70	58	63	62	53	69	26	96	671	
100	22	40	68	75	80	49	67	48	119	3	671	
34	88	82	54	47	42	73	55	74	19	103	671	
109	114	25	6	24	91	104	29	107	32	30	671	
13	8	97	116	98	31	18	93	15	90	92	671	
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	

11	mgc											671
6	107	117	36	96	109	31	24	23	16	106	671	
116	15	5	86	26	13	91	98	99	121	1	671	
94	28	82	48	45	49	81	46	76	30	92	671	
102	20	40	74	77	73	41	80	42	95	27	671	
89	33	52	70	60	59	64	55	67	18	104	671	
11	111	78	44	65	61	57	56	66	114	8	671	
110	12	39	83	58	63	62	68	54	108	14	671	
3	119	85	37	75	43	53	50	84	22	100	671	
21	101	51	71	47	79	69	72	38	25	97	671	
112	10	29	90	34	35	113	105	4	120	19	671	
7	115	93	32	88	87	9	17	118	2	103	671	
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	

11	mgc											671
12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671	
121	51	56	49	96	101	94	33	38	31	1	671	
119	50	52	54	95	97	99	32	34	36	3	671	
117	55	48	53	100	93	98	37	30	35	5	671	
115	42	47	40	60	65	58	78	83	76	7	671	
11	41	43	45	59	61	63	77	79	81	111	671	
13	46	39	44	64	57	62	82	75	80	109	671	
15	87	92	85	24	29	22	69	74	67	107	671	
17	86	88	90	23	25	27	68	70	72	105	671	
19	91	84	89	28	21	26	73	66	71	103	671	
112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671	
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	

11	mgc											671
12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671	
121	28	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	30	1	671	
119	21	78	74	76	41	40	38	80	101	3	671	
117	23	37	70	73	53	55	54	85	99	5	671	
115	25	39	50	60	65	58	72	83	97	7	671	
11	93	79	51	59	61	63	71	43	29	111	671	
13	91	77	66	64	57	62	56	45	31	109	671	
15	89	75	68	49	69	67	52	47	33	107	671	
17	87	42	48	46	81	82	84	44	35	105	671	
19	92	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	94	103	671	
112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671	
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	

See the details:

- In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 11.
 1. First one is a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 11 with magic square of order 3 is in the middle. The 4 magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 4 magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal magic sums in each case.
 2. The second one is a **cornered** magic square of order 11, where magic squares of orders 9, 7 and 5 are

- also **cornered** at the upper-left corner with magic square of order 3. The 2 magic rectangles of orders 2×3 , 2 of order 2×5 , 2 of order 2×7 and 2 of order 2×9 are of equal sums in each case.
3. The third one is again a **double-layer bordered** magic squares of orders 11 and 7 having magic square of order 3 in the middle. In this case the 2 magic rectangles of orders 2×11 , 4 of order 2×7 and 2 of order 2×3 are of equal magic sums in each case. These types of magic squares sometimes we call as **flat-double-layer bordered** magic squares.
 4. The forth is a **cyclic-double-layer bordered** with magic square of order 3 in the middle. The 4 magic rectangles of order 2×9 and 4 of order 2×5 are of equal sums in each case.
 5. The fifth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a magic square of order 9 composed of 9 equal sums magic squares of order 3.
 6. The sixth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 11 having magic square of order 3 in the middle.

Combining with 3888 magic squares of order 110 we have $6 \times 3888 = 23328$, i.e., **23328-different types** of magic squares of order 132. Since this number is too high, we worked with 648 magic squares of order 110, resulting in 3888 magic square of order 132. See below few examples in figures:

Above there are only few examples, but there are 3888 magic squares of order 132 composed of magic squares orders 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 9 and 12. More details are in an **excel file** attached with the work.

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